

THE INFLUENCE OF CHEMICAL TREATMENT ON THE INTERFACE QUALITY AND PHYSICAL PROPERTIES OF COPPER - GRAPHITE COMPOSITES

M . JAHAZI* and F . JALILIAN**

* Department of Materials Eng . , Tarbiat Modarres University
P. O. BOX 14155 - 4838 Tehran / Islamic Republic of Iran

** Department of Materials Eng . , Islamic Azad University of Tehran

ABSTRACT

High strength carbon fibers were submitted to various thermochemical treatments in order to obtain an uniform and tough coating of copper particles on thier surfaces. After heat treatment in the range 700 - 1000 °C under argon atmosphere they were chemically treated in NaOH , HNO₃, C₃H₆O and HF baths with different concentrations. The latter solution being used for the first time in this investigation.

The results, indicate that both the heat and chemical treatments influence greatly the bindig quality of copper particles to the fibers which is crucial for a reliable composite material. Heat treatment at 1000 °C for 2 hours and chemical treatment with HF led to a " porous " and groovy surface resulting in an uniform and thin layer of copper after electroplating. Microstructural evolution at different steps was followed using scanning electron microscopy and a mechanism for copper growth at the surface of the fibers is proposed. Finally, the influence of sintering conditions on electrical and thermal conductivities of the composite material was studied and the strength and composition of the interface was examined using the SEM technique.

INTRODUCTION

The application of copper - graphite composites to electrical and aerospace devices have been known for a long time [1]. Higher strength , better dimensional stability , excellent electrical and thermal conductivities make of them suitable materials both from technical

and economical considerations. Different properties are obtained by varying the proportions of copper and graphite and in some cases by the addition of alloying elements such as Sn , Zn and Pb [2]. They are made by liquid metal infiltration , electroplating and powder metallurgy techniques.

Although , carbon fibers possess excellent mechanical properties , however , it is generally not possible to transfere the latter to the composite material which presents generally low interlaminar shear strength. This weakness is related to unstable bondings at the interface of carbon fibers to copper particles. As the behaviour of the interface depends strongly on the quality of the fibers' surfaces, consequently it is of great importance to know the effect of thermal and chemical treatments on the surface of the fibers. The aim of all these surface preparations being to obtain an uniform and tough copper coating .

In this investigation the effect of surface treatments on the behaviour of carbon fibers during the electroplating stage and composite material fabrication was studied. Copper growth at the surface of the fibers and the quality of the interface was examined using scanning electron microscopy. Composite samples were prepared by powder metallurgy technique and the variation of their physical properties as a function of fibers' volume percent and other experimental parameters were studied.

MATERIALS AND METHOD

High strength carbon fibers in continous form with 350 MPa modulus and 3500 MPa strength and copper powder 99.9 % pure with an average size of less than 63 microns were used in the present investigation. The fibers were submitted to a preliminary heat treatment at 1000°C for 2 hours under argon atmosphere. This treatment achieves part of the finishing and sizing treatment given to the active fibers. It also gives result to a groovy surface devoided of the protective polymeric resin (epoxy type) increasing by this way their specific surfaces. The heat cleaned fibers were chemically treated with four solutions with different concentrations for each solution as indicated in Table 1 . The fibers were then vacuum heat treated for 1 hour at 110°C in order to remove all the solutions existing inside the grooves and holes present at their surfaces.

In order to study the copper growth mechanism, carbon fibers were mounted on special frames (about 9000 in each frame) and copper was deposited on their surfaces using electroplating (cyanide and sulphate) and electroless baths. Electroplating times of 30, 60, 90, 120, 150, 180 and 210 seconds were used in cyanide bath while electroless experiments were carried out for 600, 1200, 1800 and 2400 seconds. The amount of copper present at the surface of the fibers after each coating process was calculated using the ASTM D

3553-76 standard [3]. Also the morphology of the fibers' surface before and after coating as well as the fiber - matrix interface was examined using a cambridge - 360 scanning electron microscope.

The coated fibers after heat treatment in an hydrogen atmosphere furnace were chopped, mixed with copper powder, cold pressed and sintered according to the schedule presented in Table 2. The influence of sintering conditions and the volume percent of fibers on electrical and thermal conductivities of the composite material were studied using Eddy current and a TMA 939 Dupont apparatus respectively .

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Heat treatments were applied in the range 700 - 1000 °C for different holding times under argon atmosphere and the surface quality was examined with SEM [4]. In this study it was found that the best heat treatment resulting on the removal of the protective epoxy resin from the surface grooves is obtained by 2 hours heat treating at 1000 °C. When such fibers were coated regions devoid of copper coat were observed leading to a non uniform coat under these conditions.

In order to obtain uniform coating a chemical surface treatment which increases the number of nucleation sites and copper absorbing points is required. Four solutions HNO₃, C₃H₆O, NaOH and HF each with three different concentrations as indicated in Table 1 were employed. In order to study the effect of these chemical treatments on copper coating behaviour all the samples were electroplated in a cyanide bath for 150 seconds. A good coating in terms of thickness and uniformity was produced by NaOH 20 % wt , HNO₃ 70 % wt , C₃H₆O 98 % wt and HF 8 % wt. SEM examination of coated fibers indicate that the best results are obtained with HF. Fig. 1. shows a fiber after such chemical treatment , as it can be seen the surface of the fiber is " porous " and groovy. Under these conditions the specific surface of the fiber and the number of functional groups are higher than in other cases.

Among the three solutions used for copper coating the sulphate bath after a coating time of 1800 seconds produces a layer of 3 to 4 microns thick , while for a residence time of 3200 seconds in the electroless bath the thickness of the copper layer is less than 1 micron. The cyanide solution produces a 1 - 2 microns layer after 150 seconds. A comparison between the performance of the three solutions led to the choice of the cyanide solution for the coating process. The coated fibers were heat treated in a hydrogen atmosphere

furnace in the range 600 – 650°C for 1 hour. This was done in order to clean and remove the oxides which may be present at the surface of the fibers. The presence of the latter is detrimental to the quality of the interface and the properties of the composite material are strongly affected by it.

SEM investigation of nucleation and growth of copper particles suggests the mechanism illustrated schematically in Fig. 2. Copper particles first nucleate at preferential sites, then grow both circumferentially and in radius until full contact is reached [5]. Some axial growth is also observed in these cases but is transformed to radial growth when the current density is increased in the latter direction. In fact it was reported that copper can grow on fibers by two potential mechanisms [5,6]. The first one is when the atomic binding energy of copper to carbon fibers (E_c) is greater than the absorption energy of copper to fibers (E_a), in this case the growth follows the Volmer – Weber model and occurs in the form of small islands which become in contact after a certain time. The other mechanism proposed by Franke van der Merwe occurs when $E_c < E_a$, in this case copper grows layer by layer and consequently coating is more uniform [5].

In this investigation clusters of copper were first observed at some preferential points at the surface. As the holding time increases the clusters grow and other smaller clusters present at their neighborhood are eliminated. This was related to a decrease of current density and an overvoltage at the vicinity of smaller clusters [4]. Based on the above observations, it was concluded that in cyanide electroplating solution the nucleation and growth of copper follows the Volmer – Weber model. However, chemical surface treatment by HF seems to modify the growth mechanism from island type (Volmer – Weber) to a layer by layer (Van der Merwe) resulting in more uniform copper coat at the surface of the fibers. The interface between the coated fibers and the matrix was also studied using SEM and it was concluded as long as the fibers are coated with an uniform and thin layer of copper devoided of any pollution an excellent contact is obtained between matrix and the fibers as shown in Fig. 3.

Pure and composite samples were studied by measuring and comparing their thermal and electrical conductivities and densities. The influence of fiber volume fraction on electrical conductivity is shown in Fig. 4. As it can be seen when the volume fraction of the fibers is increased from 10 to 50 % a decrease of about 40 % in electrical conductivity is measured due probably to the lower conductivity of graphite. It was also observed that when higher pressure and temperature are applied during sintering better electrical conductivity are obtained from the composite material. This can be related to better diffusion conditions and lower porosity under the above situation. The influence of temperature and pressure become stronger as the fibers' volume fraction increases.

The effect of fiber volume fraction on composite density is illustrated in Fig. 5. The general trend indicates that the density decreases as the graphite volume fraction increases. However, it appears that doubling the powder pressure and the sintering temperature do not influence significantly the density for this composite material. Finally, the variation of the ratio of the composite material thermal conductivity to that of the matrix with fiber volume fraction was measured. The results are shown in Fig 6. A small fall is observed in CTE_c / CTE_m when the fiber volume fraction is increased. However, this fall is minimum for the most severe sintering conditions. The low thermal conductivity of graphite is probably the most important parameter for the observed decrease of the thermal conductivity.

CONCLUSIONS

- 1 - By heat treating H. S. carbon fibers at 1000°C for 2 hours and chemical preparation in 8 % wt HF it is possible to prepare the fibers for an uniform and tough coating of copper at their surfaces.
- 2 - The mechanism of copper growth follows the Volmer - Weber model when electroplating in a cyanide bath. However it appears that by HF treating the growth mechanism changes from the Volmer - Weber model to Franke Van der Merwe.
- 3 - By a suitable surface treatment it is possible to obtain copper - graphite composites with convenient physical properties.

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TABLES AND FIGURES

Table 1. Chemical surface treatment solutions

solution	concentration of solution (%wt)
HNO ₃	50 - 60 - 70
HF	5 - 8 - 13
NaOH	10 - 20 - 30
C ₃ H ₆ O	98

Table 2. Different pressing and sintering conditions applied on the samples

No.	Fibers wt %	press and sintering conditions			
1	% 4	2 ton	350°C - 2 h	5 ton	750°C - 3 h
2	% 4	3.5 ton	350°C - 2 h	5 ton	750°C - 3 h
3	% 4	3.5 ton	450°C - 2 h	5 ton	750°C - 3 h
4	% 4	—	—	8 ton	750°C - 3 h
5	% 15	2 ton	350°C - 2 h	5 ton	750°C - 3 h
6	% 15	3.5 ton	350°C - 2 h	5 ton	750°C - 3 h
7	% 15	3.5 ton	450°C - 2 h	5 ton	750°C - 3 h
8	% 15	—	—	8 ton	750°C - 3 h
9	% 25	2 ton	350°C - 2 h	5 ton	750°C - 3 h
10	% 25	3.5 ton	350°C - 2 h	5 ton	750°C - 3 h
11	% 25	3.5 ton	450°C - 2 h	5 ton	750°C - 3 h
12	% 25	—	—	8 ton	750°C - 3 h
13	—	2 ton	350°C - 2 h	5 ton	750°C - 3 h
14	—	3.5 ton	350°C - 2 h	5 ton	750°C - 3 h
15	—	3.5 ton	450°C - 2 h	5 ton	750°C - 3 h
16	—	—	—	8 ton	750°C - 3 h

Figure 1. Surface treated fibers with HF 8 % wt

Figure 2. The mechanism of copper growth on graphite fibers

Figure 3. The interface between matrix and carbon fibers

Figure 4. Effect of fiber volume fraction on electrical conductivity

Figure 5. Effect of fiber volume fraction on density

Figure 6. Effect of fiber volume fraction on thermal conductivity